

STUDIES IN VITAMIN-C OXIDATION. PART III, RETARDATION OF VITAMIN-C OXIDATION BY OXALIC ACID.

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The retardation of vitamin-C oxidation by oxalic acid has been studied in detail. It has been found that oxalic acid inhibits markedly the oxidation of vitamin-C under different conditions: (i) the uncatalysed oxidation, (ii) the oxidation catalysed by Cu^{++} and Fe^{++} , and (iii) the oxidation catalysed by the enzyme ascorbic acid oxidase. The mechanism of the inhibition is discussed.

The oxidation of vitamin-C in aqueous solution has been the subject of investigation by numerous workers. Minute quantities of Cu^{++} often present in distilled water or in reagents are sufficient to catalyse the oxidation of vitamin-C. The catalytic effect of traces of Cu^{++} is so marked that it is difficult to decide whether the autoxidation of ascorbic acid often noticed by several workers in the absence of added Cu^{++} may not be due to the presence of traces of Cu^{++} present as an impurity. Kellie and Zilva (*Biochem. J.*, 1935, 29, 1028) found that if ascorbic acid was dissolved in pure water, distilled from quartz vessels, it was as stable as in the solid form. Barron and co-workers (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1936, 112, 625) found that recrystallised natural ascorbic acid dissolved in the purest water did not undergo any autoxidation upto p_{H} 7.6. But Ghosh (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 1) reported that synthetic ascorbic acid underwent oxidation between p_{H} 5.8 and 7.2 in water giving a negative test for Cu^{++} with rubeanic acid or sodium diethyldithiocarbamate. McFarlane (*Biochem. J.*, 1936, 30, 1472) found that the catalytic oxidation of ascorbic acid by Cu^{++} was inhibited by sodium diethyldithiocarbamate, cystein and cystine. The inhibition of vitamin-C oxidation by sulphhydryl compounds like glutathione and cystein has been studied by Caro and Giani (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1934, 228, 13), Hopkins and Morgan (*Biochem. J.*, 1936, 30, 1446), Bersin, Koster and Justaz (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1935, 288, 12), and Ghosh and Rakshit (*Biochem. Z.*, 1936, 289, 15). Inhibition was also obtained by using oxidised forms of these compounds. The inhibition of the Cu^{++} catalysed oxidation of vitamin-C by pyrophosphate has been studied by Giri (*Indian. J. Med. Res.*, 1937, 25, 443; *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1937, 248, 185) and Krishnamurthy and Giri (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1941, 29, 71).

Ascorbic acid which undergoes rapid oxidation either spontaneous or catalysed *in vitro*, is strangely enough stable in vegetable and in animal

tissues. Thus Caro and Gianì (*loc.cit.*) found that tissue pulp and aqueous, alcoholic and trichloroacetic acid extracts of tissues inhibit the oxidation of ascorbic acid *in vitro*. Mawson (*Biochem. J.*, 1935, 29, 569) also found that small amounts of animal tissue extracts prevent the aerobic oxidation of ascorbic acid. It is evident that animal tissues contain certain substances, which can inhibit the oxidation of vitamin-C. Two such substances may be glutathione and cystein. It has been shown (Krishnamurthy and Giri *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 7) that out of as many as 26 substances, which exert inhibitory action on the oxidation of the vitamin in presence of Cu^{++} , oxalic acid appeared to be a powerful retarder. Hence the author has now studied in detail the mechanism of inhibition by oxalic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

10 ml. of *M/5*-acetic acid-acetate buffer (p_H 5.6) was kept in a conical flask; the requisite quantity of oxalic acid solution, brought to the same p_H by neutralisation with sodium carbonate solution containing 5 mg. of the vitamin, and then enough water to make up the total volume to 25 ml. were added. The mixture was shaken well and 2 ml. pipetted out and added to 1 ml. of glacial acetic acid and titrated immediately with 2 : 6-dichlorophenolindophenol. All the experiments were conducted at $37^\circ \pm 0.1$. All the solutions employed in this investigation were made up with water, twice distilled in glass vessels.

In Table I are given the results on the retardation of ascorbic acid oxidation at different concentrations in the absence of added Cu^{++} . The percentage of inhibition is calculated from the following formula.

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = 100 \left(1 - \frac{\text{Amt. oxidised in 1 hr. with oxalic acid}}{\text{Amt. oxidised in 1 hr. without oxalic acid}} \right).$$

TABLE I.

Influence of oxalic acid on the spontaneous oxidation of vitamin-C.

Oxalic acid conc.	Percentage of vitamin-C oxidised.			% Inhibition
	0 min.	30 min.	60 min.	
Nil	0	26	44	...
$2 \times 10^{-3} M.$	0	0	2	95
1×10^{-2}	0	0	2	95
1×10^{-3}	0	6	16	65
1×10^{-4}	0	18	34	26
1×10^{-5}	0	22	36	17
1×10^{-6}	0	26	42	Nil

It is evident from the above results that oxalic acid even in minute concentrations is able to protect the spontaneous oxidation in aqueous

solution of vitamin-C. These results also show that vitamin-C undergoes oxidation at p_H 5.6 even in the absence of added Cu^{++} , in agreement with the results of Ghosh (*loc. cit.*).

The results recorded in Table II show that oxalic acid can retard the oxidation of ascorbic acid even when catalysed by Cu^{++} ions. Blank experiments have shown that oxalic acid has no action on the indophenol dye under the conditions of the experiments.

It was thought that this inhibition might be due to complex formation between the oxalic acid and the copper ions. Hence in the experiments, the results where of are recorded in Table III, the concentration of oxalic acid was kept constant at $M/50$ and the concentration of Cu^{++} altered. For comparison the corresponding results without oxalic acid are also given.

TABLE II.

Influence of oxalic acid on the oxidation of vitamin-C catalysed by Cu^{++}

Reagent: 10 ml. acetate buffer (p_H 5.6) + 5 mg. of ascorbic acid + 0.07 mg. $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ + oxalic acid + water to make 25 ml.

Oxalic acid conc.	Percentage of vitamin-C oxidised.			% Inhibition.
	0 min.	30 min.	60 min.	
Nil	0	54	76	...
2×10^{-3} M	0	4	8	89
1×10^{-2}	0	10	16	79
1×10^{-3}	0	32	52	33
1×10^{-4}	0	44	66	17
1×10^{-5}	0	44	66	17
1×10^{-6}	0	52	74	4

TABLE III.

Effect of variation of Cu concentration on the inhibition of vitamin-C oxidation by oxalic acid.

The reaction mixture consisted of 10 ml. of acetate buffer (p_H 5.6), 5 mg. of ascorbic acid, copper sulphate solution, $M/50$ -oxalic acid in the total volume, and water to make up 25 ml.

% Conc. of $CuSO_4$ in soln.	Percentage of vitamin-C oxidised.						% Inhibition.
	Without oxalic acid.			With oxalic acid.			
	0 min.	30 min.	60 min.	0 min.	30 min.	60 min.	
Nil	0	26	44	0	0	2	95
0.28mg.	0	52	76	0	4	8	89
0.82	0	62	84	0	10	22	73
1.68	0	64	86	0	18	30	65
2.52	0	64	85	0	22	34	60
3.08	0	62	84	0	22	34	59
4.20	0	62	84	0	22	36	57

The results indicate that if the concentration of Cu^{++} is increased, keeping the concentration of oxalic acid constant, the rate of oxidation of ascorbic acid increases, in other words, the inhibitory effect of oxalic acid diminishes.

In the following table are recorded the results on the influence of oxalic acid on ascorbic acid oxidation at p_H 7.2.

TABLE IV.

Influence of oxalic acid on ascorbic acid oxidation at p_H 7.2.

The reaction mixture consisted of 15 ml. of $M/15$ -phosphate buffer (p_H 7.2), 5 mg of ascorbic acid, 0.07 mg. of CuSO_4 , 5 H_2O , oxalic acid and water to make 25 ml.

Conc. of oxalic acid.	Percentage of vitamin-C oxidised.			% Inhibition
	0 min.	30 min.	60 min.	
Nil	0	52	76	...
$2 \times 10^{-3} M$	0	32	46	39
1×10^{-2}	0	40	54	29
4×10^{-3}	0	42	56	26

A comparison of the results in Tables IV and II shows that for corresponding concentrations of oxalic acid, the retardation at p_H 5.6 is more than at the alkaline p_H 7.2.

Influence of Oxalic Acid on the Oxidation of Vitamin-C catalysed by Fe^{++}

The results in the following table show that Fe^{++} ions exert, though to a limited extent, some catalytic effect on the oxidation of the vitamin in aqueous solution at p_H 5.6 and that oxalic acid retards the catalysed oxidation.

TABLE V.

The reaction mixture consisted of 10 ml. of $M/5$ -acetate buffer (p_H 5.6), 5 mg. of ascorbic acid, 0.7 mg. of FeSO_4 , 7 H_2O , oxalic acid, and water to make 25 ml.

Conc. of oxalic acid.	Percentage of vitamin-C oxidised.			% Inhibition.
	0 min.	30 min.	60 min.	
Nil	0	38	56	...
$2 \times 10^{-3} M$	0	8	14	75
1×10^{-2}	0	10	20	64
4×10^{-3}	0	14	24	57
2×10^{-2}	0	16	26	53

Influence of Oxalic Acid on the Enzymic Oxidation of Ascorbic Acid.

Tauber (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1935, 110, 211) isolated from the pericarp of Hubbard squash an enzyme, ascorbic acid oxidase, which rapidly oxidised vitamin-C in aqueous solution. The presence of a similar enzyme has been reported in vegetables by numerous workers, notably Srinivasan (*Current Sci.*, 1935, 4, 407), Chakrabarty and Guha (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1937, 24, 839). The enzyme has been found to be highly specific for ascorbic acid. Recently Krishnamurthy and Giri (*loc. cit.*) found that pyrophosphate (which is found to inhibit the Cu^{++} catalysed oxidation of ascorbic acid) has little influence on the enzymic oxidation.

It will be of considerable interest to study the influence of oxalic acid on the oxidation of the vitamin, catalysed by the enzyme. Hence in the following experiments such a study has been made using an enzyme preparation obtained from *Cucumis sativus* according to the method described in Part I of this series.

In the following table are given the results of the influence of varying concentrations of oxalic acid on the vitamin-C oxidation with a constant concentration of the enzyme solution.

TABLE VI.

Influence of oxalic acid on the enzymic oxidation of vitamin-C.

The reaction mixture consisted of 10 ml. of acetate buffer (pH 5.6), 5 mg. of ascorbic acid, 1 ml. enzyme solution, oxalic acid and water to make up 25 ml.

Conc of oxalic acid.	Percentage of vitamin-C oxidised.			% Inhibition.
	0 min.	30 min.	60 min.	
Nil,	0	68	58	...
$4 \times 10^{-3} M$	0	26	36	63
2×10^{-3}	0	42	70	29
1×10^{-3}	0	56	88	10
4×10^{-4}	0	58	92	6

A comparison of the results in Tables VI and II show that the same concentration of oxalic acid retards the enzymatic oxidation to a smaller extent than that of Cu^{++} catalysed oxidation. For instance, a concentration of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ oxalic acid retards the enzymatic oxidation to the extent of only 10 %, while it retards the Cu^{++} -catalysed reaction to the extent

of 79%. It is to be noted, however, that even with the enzymic oxidation increased retardation is obtained at higher concentrations of oxalic acid.

In the following table are recorded the results of experiments in which the enzyme concentration was varied while the oxalic acid concentration was kept constant.

TABLE VII.

Effect of variation of enzyme concentration on the inhibition of enzymatic oxidation of vitamin-C by Cu^{++} .

The reaction mixture consisted of 10 ml. of acetate buffer (pH 5.6), 5 mg of ascorbic acid, enzyme solution, oxalic acid to make to a total concentration of $M/50$, and water to make up 25 ml.

Enzyme solution.	Percentage of vitamin-C oxidised.		
	0 min.	30 min.	60 min.
Nil	0	0	2
1.0 ml.	0	42	70
0.75	0	44	68
0.50	0	40	62
0.25	0	24	40
0.10	0	18	28

The results indicate that the inhibition by given concentration of oxalic acid is more pronounced at lower concentrations of the enzyme than at the higher. It is possible that oxalic acid retards by forming a complex with the enzyme also.

DISCUSSION.

The results presented in this paper show that oxalic acid can markedly retard the oxidation of ascorbic acid under different conditions, namely (1) the uncatalysed oxidation, (2) the oxidation catalysed by Cu^{++} and Fe^{++} ions, and (3) the oxidation catalysed by the enzyme ascorbic acid oxidase. The inhibition is manifest even at such low concentrations as $1 \times 10^{-6} M$, while $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ concentration of oxalic acid affords almost complete protection for the Cu^{++} -catalysed reaction. Oxalic acid affords a certain measure of protection of the vitamin even against enzymic oxidation. The presence of oxalic acid and other acids like tartaric, citric, etc. which have also been found (reported in Part II of this series) to markedly inhibit the

oxidation of the vitamin, explains the stability of the vitamin in several plant tissues.

Fujita and Iwatake (*Biochem. Z.*, 1935, 275, 291) proposed the addition of metaphosphoric acid to the liquid used in extracting the vitamin from plant tissues in order to prevent its oxidation and to ensure more reliable results. Giri (*loc. cit.*) proposed the use of pyrophosphate for a similar purpose. Now the results recorded in this paper show that the degree of retardation produced by oxalic acid is much higher than that produced either by metaphosphoric acid or sodium pyrophosphate at corresponding concentrations. The addition of oxalic acid to the extracting fluid should, therefore, ensure more reliable results in the estimation of vitamin-C in plant and animal tissues. Moreover, the use of oxalic acid should prove more economical, as the cost of phosphoric acid and pyrophosphate is high.

It will be of interest to study the mechanism of this retardation produced by oxalic acid. In Part II of this series it has been suggested by us that an inhibitor may work by three alternative mechanisms.

- (1) It may form a complex with the catalyst,
- (2) It may form a more stable compound with the substrate namely ascorbic acid.
- (3) It may act as a hydrogen donator capable of reducing the oxidised form of the vitamin back to the original form.

Hopkins and Morgan (*Biochem. J.*, 1935, 80, 1446) found that glutathione markedly inhibits the oxidation of ascorbic acid. They explained the inhibitory action of glutathione as being due to its capacity to reduce dehydroascorbic acid to ascorbic acid.

This suggestion is confirmed by the work of Borsook and Jeffries (*Science*, 1936, 83, 397) who found that the reduced form of glutathione can actually reduce dehydroascorbic acid to ascorbic acid.

The author made experiments to see if oxalic acid can reduce dehydroascorbic acid, with negative results. Hence mechanism (3) is not possible in this case. The bulk of the evidence adduced in this paper shows that very likely oxalic acid acts by forming a complex with the catalyst, the Cu^{++} , Fe^{++} , or the enzyme, though it should be noted here that inhibition was obtained even for the uncatalysed oxidation. It is well known that

oxalic acid and oxalates form complex salts with Cu^{++} and Fe^{++} , as for instance

The concentration of oxalic acid used in each of the experiments is enough to form the complex with Cu^{++} or Fe^{++} , and the concentration of oxalic acid does not appear to decrease during the reaction.

Further work is in progress.

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